

Traditional Uses of Medicinal Plants in Treating Snake Bite and Skin Diseases in Chandgad tahsil of Kolhapur District of Maharashtra, India

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Abstract:

An ethnomedicinal survey was under taken to collect information from local rural people about the use of medicinal plants in Kolhapur district. Local people use certain folklore medicinal plants for the treatment of snake bite and skin diseases. The present paper documents the traditional knowledge of medicinal plant species used to cure snake bite and various types of skin diseases in Kolhapur district. Ethnomedicinal information of medicinal plants was taken from different localities of Kolhapur district by interview with local rural practitioners (vaidya). The knowledge about the medicinal plant has been transmitted orally from generation to generation. The investigation revealed that there are about 10 species of plants used to treat snake bite and 12 species of plants used to cure various types of skin diseases like scabies, psoriasis, eczema, ring worms etc. The medicinal plants used to cure snake bite and skin diseases are enumerated disease wise with botanical name, family, local name, part used and mode of administration. The study indicates that the local inhabitants rely on medicinal plants for treatment. The traditional knowledge of medicinal plants has great potential for research and the discovery of new drugs.

Keywords: Traditional, Snake bite, Skin diseases, Kolhapur District.

Introduction:

Plants have been used in traditional medicine for several thousand years. The knowledge of medicinal plants has been accumulated in the course of many centuries based on different medicinal system such as Ayurveda, Unani and Siddha. In India, it is reported that traditional healers use 2500 plant species and 100 species of plants serves as a regular sources of medicine (Pei, 2001).

During last few decades there has been an increase in the study of medicinal plants and their traditional uses in different parts of the world (Lev, 2006). Herbal remedies are considered the oldest form of health care known to mankind on this earth. Prior to the development of modern medicine the traditional system of medicine that have evolved over the centuries within various communities are still maintained as a great traditional knowledge base in herbal medicines (Mukharjee and Wahli, 2006). Traditionally this treasure of knowledge has been passed on orally from generation to generation without any written document (Perumal Samy and Ignachimuthu, 2000) and is still retained by various indigenous groups around the world. Documenting the indigenous knowledge through ethnomedicinal studies is important for the conservation and utilization of biological resources. Ethnobotanical survey

has been found to be one of the reliable approach to drug discovery (Fabricant and Farnsworth, 2001). Several active compounds have been discovered from plants on the basis of ethnobotanical information and used directly as patented drugs (Carney et al., 1999). It is an urgent need to collect and conserve all ethnobotanical information's from various communities.

Material and Methods:

For gathering information regarding plants used medicinally by rural vaidus several field trips were undertaken in villages of Kolhapur district in different seasons since June 2010. Ethnobotanical data were collected according to the methodology suggested by Jain 1987. Information's (local name, mode of preparation, medicinal uses) were collected through questionnaires, interviews and discussion among rural practitioners (vaidu) in their local language and recorded in field note book. Collected information was cross checked with the help of available literature (Agarwal and Ghosh 1985, Jain 1991, Naik 1998). Specimens were collected from the field and identified with the help of local flora (Yadav and Sardesai 2002). It is our pleasure that each local informant (vaidu) have given us full support for collection details of individual plant species. The study also involved an extensive

literature search and herbarium examination (Jain 1965, Thirumalai et al. 2010, Tiwari and Padhye 1993, Upadhaye et al. 1986)

Observations

The plant species are given below with their Botanic name, Family, Local name, medicinal uses and Administration of disease in table 1.

Result and Discussion:

Present investigation revealed that 10 plant species are used for treatment of snake bite and 11 plant species are used for treatment of various skin diseases. This indicates that rural people of this region possess good knowledge of herbal drugs but their continuous and progressive exposure to modernization may result in extinction of the rich heritage of knowledge in course of time. Plant species used to treat snake bite and skin diseases belongs to family Apocynaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Icacinaceae, Liliaceae, Periplocaceae, Rubiaceae, Rutaceae and Verbenaceae. Observations revealed that the leaf is the most common crude drug in their preparations to cure diseases. Most plants used to treat snake bite and skin diseases were herbs and shrubs. Ethnobotanical data may provide a base to start the search for new compounds related to photochemistry, pharmacology and pharmacognosy. This may provide new source of herbal drugs and help to understand the molecular basis of their activities. Moreover it may further be mentioned that over exploitation of these species in the name of medicine may lead some species ultimately to the disappearance in future. Therefore attention should also be made on exploitation and proper utilization of these medicinal plants.

Acknowledgement:

Authors are cordially grateful to the people inhabiting in different localities of Kolhapur district for their kind support and co-operation during the field survey. Authors are also thankful to University Grant Commission for financial assistance.

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Table 1: List of Medicinal Plants with Botanical Name, Family, Local name, Part used and Administration

Sr. No.	Botanical name, Family and Local name	Part used	Administration
❖ Snakebite			
1	<i>Asparagus racemosus</i> Willd. Liliaceae; Shatawari, Shevari	Root	One cup root extract given orally twice a day for fifteen days.
2	<i>Cipadessa baccifera</i> (Roth) Miq. Meliaceae; Narang	Leaf	One glass leaf decoction taken internally twice for one month.
3	<i>Clerodendrum serratum</i> (L.) Verbenaceae; Bharangi	Root	One cup root extract given orally twice a day and root paste applied on bitten area.
4	<i>Gloriosa superba</i> L. Liliaceae; Kal-Lawi	Root tubers	One cup root tuber extract given twice for five days.
5	<i>Hemidesmus indicus</i> (L.) Periplocaceae; Anantmul	Root	One cup root paste taken orally for seven days.
6	<i>Leucas stelligera</i> Wall. Lamiaceae; Shankaroba	Leaf	Two tea spoon juice given with water twice a day and leaf paste applied on bitten area.
7	<i>Lobelia nicotianaefolia</i> Roth. ex R.& S. Lobeliaceae; Ran tambakhu	Leaf	Leaf paste applied on bitten area.
8	<i>Nothapodytes nimmoniana</i> (Grah.) Icacinaceae; Amruta, Narakya	Bark and Leaf	Bark and leaf extract given for seven days.
9	<i>Rauwolfia serpentina</i> (L.) Apocynaceae; Sarpagandha	Leaf	Leaf juice along with <i>Holarrhena pubescence</i> bark juice taken twice a day for seven days
10	<i>Toddalia asiatica</i> (L.) Rutaceae; Jangli mirachi	Leaf	One cup leaf extract given orally three times for seven days.
❖ Skin Diseases			
1	<i>Achyranthus aspera</i> L. Amaranthaceae; Aghada	Leaf	Leaf paste with onion applied over infected part of skin.
2	<i>Ageratum conyzoids</i> L. Asteraceae; Sahdevi	Leaf	Crushed leaves applied on ringworms.
3	<i>Aloe vera</i> (L.) Liliaceae; Korphad	Leaf	Fresh leaf juice applied to cure scabies.
4	<i>Azadirachta indica</i> Juss. Meliaceae; Neem	Leaf	Crushed leaves applied on ringworm.
5	<i>Cassia tora</i> L. Caesalpiniaceae; Takala	Seeds	Seeds ground with butter milk and paste applied over infected skin.
6	<i>Cipadessa baccifera</i> (Roth) Meliaceae; Narang	Root and Leaf	Root and leaf paste applied over infected skin.
7	<i>Clerodendrum serratum</i> (L.) Moon. Verbenaceae; Bharangi	Leaf	Leaf juice applied over infected skin.
8	<i>Euphorbia hirta</i> L. Euphorbiaceae; Dudhali	Leaf	Crushed leaves applied over affected skin.
9	<i>Randia dumetorum</i> Lamk.	Seeds	Fruits rubbed and applied on infected skin.

	Rubiaceae; Gela	and fruits	
10	<i>Toddalia asiatica</i> (L.) Rutaceae; Jangli mirachi	Leaf	Leaf paste applied over infected skin.
11	<i>Vitex negundo</i> L. Verbenaceae ; Nirgundi	Leaf	Leaf juice mixed with leaf juice of <i>Achyranthus aspera</i> and applied over infected part of skin.
12	<i>Woodfordia fruticosa</i> (L.) Kurz. Lythraceae; Dhayati	Leaf	Fresh leaf paste applied on infected part of skin.